

BUTANEXT: NEXT GENERATION BIOBUTANOL

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ABSTRACT: Biobutanol is an exciting alternative to first generation biofuels due to its physical and chemical characteristics, making it more fuel efficient and suitable for use in spark ignition and diesel engines without the need for modification. However, due to the inefficiencies and costs associated with the current production process, biobutanol is yet to gain market establishment. The ButaNexT project will develop highly efficient production processes for the conversion of sustainable feedstocks into the next generation biobutanol. This will contribute to overcoming the current challenges and limitations exhibited by first generation biofuels.

The ButaNexT consortium is a multi-disciplinary team of SMEs, large companies and research centres from Belgium, the Netherlands, Spain and the United Kingdom. The team aspires to optimise each stage of the biobutanol production value chain: biomass pre-treatment, enzymatic hydrolysis, fermentation, downstream processing and blending. It is expected that ButaNexT will achieve significant reductions in both production costs (up to 50%, to attain price-parity with first generation biofuels) and carbon emissions (up to 85%) compared with fossil fuels (gasoline and diesel). Moreover, the project is working on maximising the biobutanol conversion yields from selected lignocellulosic feedstocks such as wheat straw, miscanthus and the organic fraction of Municipal Solid Waste.

Keywords: biofuel, fermentation, miscanthus, municipal solid waste, wheat straw, pilot plant.

1 INTRODUCTION

Conventional, first generation biofuels (ethanol and biodiesel) are produced from renewable sources and are helpful to reduce our dependence on transportation fuels derived from finite petroleum sources. However, some of these biofuels show limitations relating to sustainability, high production costs, performance properties and incompatibility with existing infrastructures. Thus, currently some advanced biofuels (for example biobutanol) based on more sustainable feedstocks and more efficient technologies are being developed in order to overcome these limitations and meet sustainability and fuel quality standards.

Biobutanol is an attractive advanced biofuel with superior fuel properties [1]. It fits the existing fuel infrastructure; has a higher energy density (similar to petrol/gasoline) and has shown better performance properties than ethanol and biodiesel; however it has not yet been established in the market due to some technical and economic barriers.

In this project, we aim to overcome some of those barriers by developing and demonstrating, at pilot scale, a novel integrated process for producing cost-competitive biobutanol from sustainable renewable feedstocks. More specifically the key project differentiators are:

- A focus on sustainable feedstocks (wheat straw, miscanthus and organic fiber from municipal waste) that are not only low cost but also offer tremendous societal and environmental benefits relating to waste minimization and GHG (1) emissions reduction.
- The design and construction of a capital-efficient biomass milling prototype that significantly reduces feedstock particle size. The net result is higher

conversion yields in subsequent stages and a lower energy balance. This technology, developed by Técnicas Reunidas (TR), is relatively simple, scalable and can be applied to difficult feedstocks such as hard-wood biomass (willow, oak) and processing waste food (olive pits, apricot pit)

- The development of cellulase enzyme cocktails specifically for *Clostridium* taking advantage of *Clostridium*'s unique fermentation and sugar uptake characteristics. The objective is to reduce the type of enzymes and loadings, reducing hydrolysis time and more significantly enzyme cost.
- The redesign of the conventional acetone-butanol-ethanol (ABE) fermentation (2). Partner GBL's (Greenbiologics Ltd.) advanced microbes produce solvents at butanol ratios in high solvent yielding fermentations. This lends itself to new energy efficient separation methods (see *in situ* removal technique described below). In addition, GBL has developed an advanced fermentation process that produces butanol at high productivity (low volumetric productivities are a limitation with the conventional ABE batch process).
- The use and integration of a method for *in situ* butanol removal and separation using pervaporation developed by partner VITO. This method is energy efficient and also reduces end product inhibition resulting in a step change in overall solvent titres and productivity. This novel separation method also allows the use of more concentrated sugar streams reducing feedstock dilution and the water requirement. This approach results in lower energy costs in the downstream processing compared to the conventional distillation section for product

purification.

- Demonstrate the efficacy of using biobutanol as both a fuel extender of conventional fuels (gasoline and diesel) but also as a superior fuel additive that improves the properties of existing biofuel blends (ethanol, biodiesel and E85 (3)). This work will be developed by partner UCLM.

All process stages and technologies mentioned above will be integrated, optimized and demonstrated in a pilot facility owned by partner CENER. In addition, partner E4tech will demonstrate significant societal benefits relating to waste minimization, reduced air pollution, reduced GHG emissions and job and wealth creation within the EU.

In summary, ButaNexT aims to develop and validate a cheaper, more energy saving, social and environmentally friendly integrated process able to efficiently convert sustainable feedstocks (lignocellulosic biomass and wastes) into biobutanol and define optimal biobutanol blends with fossil fuels and conventional biofuels (ethanol and biodiesel).

2 DESCRIPTION OF WORK

2.1 Overall project concept

ButaNexT aims to develop, optimize and integrate several novel and advanced technologies for the production of sustainable, more efficient and versatile biobutanol from lignocellulosic feedstocks and wastes by addressing the following technical, economic and environmental challenges:

- Efficient Conversion of Lignocellulosic Feedstocks into Fermentable Sugars through physical and thermochemical pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis.
- High Productivity Fermentation for Biobutanol with “in-situ” product recovery.
- Process Integration and Scale-up.
- Techno/Economic Feasibility of Advanced Biofuels Production.
- Blending and Performance.
- Environmental and Social Benefits Assessment of Advanced Biofuels Production.

2.2 ButaNexT work package structure

The project is structured in seven work packages (Figure 1). WP1 comprises project coordination & management activities.

Figure 1: ButaNexT WP Scheme

WP2 (Biomass Supply, Pretreatment & Enzymatic Hydrolysis) aims to develop a versatile pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis technology compatible with three representative and relevant European lignocellulosic feedstocks: wheat straw, miscanthus and organic fiber (treated organic fraction of MSW). Pretreatment development includes an **efficient milling method** feasible at industrial scale and a mild thermochemical stage, minimizing the overall energy demand, limiting costs and ensuring the best resulting pre-treated biomass.

The **design and construction of a milling prototype** is being carried out based on lab-scale previous experience.

In parallel an optimization of the thermochemical pretreatment conditions is being carried out in order to assess conversion yields and inhibitors production taking into account integration with enzymatic hydrolysis

Complementarily, **a tailor-made enzymatic cocktail is being developed** for the pretreated feedstocks used in **ButaNexT** to allow an efficient fermentation of the hydrolysates.

WP3 is focussed on the **Development & Validation of High Productivity Butanol Fermentation**. The goal is the validation of a low cost route to n-butanol from C5 & C6 sugars obtained from pretreated feedstocks in WP2. Key features of this WP include the **development of superior microbes** that can ferment hydrolysed feedstocks into butanol at high yield (target 0.25g/g sugar) and the **validation at lab and bench scale of a high productivity continuous fermentation process in combination with in-situ product recovery (ISPR) that extends butanol production**. The target is to achieve an average productivity of 0.75 g/L/h from cellulosic sugars **ISPR** is a technique to remove inhibitory butanol from the fermentor and hence increase productivities.

WP4 will integrate process information and results obtained in WPs 2, & 3, in order to **develop and validate an integrated lignocellulosic biomass to butanol process**. After that, the development of whole process conversion assays will be carried out at CENER's Second Generation Biofuels Centre (CB2G). This is a **pilot facility open for practice oriented education, training or knowledge exchange**. The deliverables include performance and validation tests on the whole production process for the selected feedstocks

The technical feasibility of using butanol as an alternative blend component for fossil fuels (gasoline and diesel) and conventional biofuels (bioethanol, biodiesel and E85) will be validated in WP5. Analysis of the properties of **blended biofuels and engine and vehicle performance tests** measuring both performance and emissions (exhaust gases, particulate matter, etc.) will be carried out. Since the reactivity of particles (which depends on composition, morphology, functional groups, size distribution, etc.) is the main parameter governing both the post-treatment techniques (DPF regeneration (4)) and the environmental implications, a complete characterization will be carried out in order to exhaustively analyze the effect of butanol.

WP6 (Environmental, resource, techno-economic and social impacts assessment) will use the integrated process design brief developed in WP3 to assess the techno-economic performance, and environmental and social impacts. The WP deliverables will include an energy balance and GHG emissions assessment, comparing biobutanol to 1st generation biofuels and

conventional transportation fuels. These workbooks will accommodate the main design and performance parameters. Also, the alternative use of feedstocks outside the bioenergy sector will be assessed. It will also deliver an economic evaluation of the integrated process to produce butanol from lignocellulosic feedstocks. Furthermore, a report on the potential **societal benefits**, such as the creation of highly skilled jobs, rural development and the potential contribution to renewable energy and GHG emission reduction targets will be carried out.

Finally WP7 will be focussed on Dissemination & Exploitation of the results. The exploitable results of the project are being identified and, if necessary, will be patent protected. All findings relevant for the **commercial exploitation and market take up** of the R&D results of the project are being consolidated in one **business plan** for each of the individual exploitable results, which will be tested and validated with potential end-users before publication of a final Exploitation Plan.

In parallel of the exploitation activities, a **dissemination strategy** will be designed and implemented aimed at bringing the knowledge produced in the project to the relevant stakeholders in industry, academia and policy making circles. To this end, a series of **knowledge exchange activities** will be organised, including technical tours of CENER's facility to showcase the project installations and better describe the processes developed within the project.

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The preliminary results achieved during the first 12 months of the project are described in the following sections.

3.1 Biomass supply, pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis

The first task performed by TR was a complete characterization of the three feedstocks supplied for the project in order to quantify the sugar contents. The results (see table I), matched the expected values ([2], [3]) for both wheat straw and miscanthus. Regarding the sugar contents of a municipal solid waste, the characterisation results indicated that the available feedstock had a much lower concentration of sugars, with only 13% w/w versus the $\approx 45\%$ expected ([4], [5]). Therefore, this initial analysis yielded that this residue was not suited for the project.

Table I: Feedstocks characterization results

		Glucan %ww	Xylan % ww	Lignin % ww			Ash %ww	Moisture %ww
				Insoluble	Soluble	Total		
Wheat straw	Av	40,32	24,46	9,78	3,02	12,80	4,65	7,98
	SD	0,00	0,12	0,03	0,04	0,07	0,05	0,30
Miscanthus	Av	46,57	20,42	16,30	1,77	17,87	0,02	8,95
	SD	0,57	0,25	0,28	0,07	0,07	0,01	0,01
MSW	Av	9,43	2,51	15,05	3,22	18,02	0,52	5,76
	SD	0,01	0,01	0,35	0,04	0,04	0,14	1,60

Physical Pretreatment

Work on developing a physical pre-treatment prototype was started by TR parallel to the feedstock

characterisation. The objective of the physical pre-treatment stage is the development of an efficient micronizing unit able to precisely control particle size output in the range 150-450 μm , which is required to increase the accessible surface area, thus, improving the hydrolysis yield during thermochemical pre-treatment stage.

This portable prototype must include all the required elements to achieve the objectives, namely, mill, sieves, mass transport system, etc. It should be noted that the fine powder produced needs to be handled with extreme caution since it is volatile and could easily catch on fire. Therefore, all the prototype elements should be selected to minimize this, following, as closely as possible, the methodology provided by the ATEX (5) protection standard.

The selection of each of the prototype elements was carried out based on performance, energy consumption and safety. Three mills (hammer mill, ring mill, cutting mill) were evaluated with each feedstock with the results summarized in the table below (Table II). The cutting mill was selected as the best suited.

Table II: Milling study results

Variables	Mills		
	Hammer	Ring	Cutting
Energy consumption (Kw/h)	12	0,75	2,2
Feeding speed (Kg biomass/h)	1,6-4	1,08	2,4-7,5
Efficiency (Kg biomass milled <450 μm /Kg biomass milled)	50-70	99	100
Weight lost (%)	7-13	3-10	0
Dust emission	Yes	Yes	No
Pre-milling	No	Yes	No

Similarly, a study on available technologies for sieving was carried out, and continuous sieving equipment was selected for the integration.

Finally, several alternatives were contemplated to transport the fine powder from one stage to the next. As previously mentioned, due to the explosive nature of this fine powder, all mechanical means of transporting this material were quickly discarded and an air based system was designed for the task. This system consists of a series of linked cyclones that suck the powder from each station and safely move it to the next stage without any emission of particulates. This system is assisted by an automatic control unit to simplify operation.

Thermochemical pretreatment study

There are three main goals in this task in order to make the cellulose polymers accessible for further conversion. First, is necessary to achieve a liquid fraction rich in xylose (Xyl) content; second, to identify and reduce the content of inhibitors in the liquid fraction, and third, to avoid the degradation of the cellulose fraction into C6 sugars (Glucose (Gl) hydrolyzed or lost).

Two different thermochemical pretreatment technologies (low solids batch and high solid continuous) are being used by TR and CENER respectively, for the purposes above mentioned.

Since the chemical pre-treatment stage is aimed at

producing the precursor for a specific task in the biobutanol production process, the identification of inhibitors was heavily based on the requirements of the project. An initial shortlist of common inhibitors ([6], [7]) selected as potential objectives the following ones: 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), Furfural (FF), Acetic acid (AA), Levulinic acid (LA), Formic acid (FA). While all inhibitors play a role of degrading performance yield, special emphasis was put on AA due to its high concentration and the effect it has in the following stages.

The thermochemical pre-treatment study was carried out only for wheat straw and miscanthus, having discarded, by consensus, the municipal solid waste early on due to its low sugar content.

Regarding low-solid batch thermochemical technology, three optimisation studies were performed with different weightings for each of the objectives of the study. The results are summarised in table III.

Table III: Thermochemical statistical study results

	Miscanthus			Wheat Straw		
	Gl g/l	Xyl g/l	AA g/l	Gl g/l	Xyl g/l	AA g/l
Optimization A	2.6	23.9	4.2	4.6	28.2	3.6
Optimization B	2.45	23	3.7	4.86	28.04	3.45
Optimization C	1.94	22.5	3.6	-	-	-

Optimisation A aimed at estimating the maximum xylose concentration achievable within the range of values studied and without considering the concentration of the other species. The results show that 78% [7] of the xylose in the miscanthus and 62% [8] in the wheat straw were transferred to the liquid fraction, well above the target values.

Optimisation B and C (C only for miscanthus) complemented A by including the other two objectives, this is, minimising the glucose in the liquid fraction and minimising the concentration of AA. Both B and C use the same approach in which, with the main goal of maximising xylose concentration, the focus was to reduce the concentration of AA first and improve on glucose loss second. Actually, optimisation C is just an extension of B in which the particle size variable was fixed to the upper limit.

When comparing the results for B and C for miscanthus, a small reduction in concentration is visible in all elements, namely 4-6% for xylose, 12-14% for AA and 6-25% for glucose. This is very good in general terms since the loss of xylose in the liquid fraction is minimal compared to the positive reduction of the concentration of the other two elements. Furthermore, optimisation C clearly indicates that a larger particle size is preferred if the aim is to reduce glucose and AA concentrations in the liquid fraction. This are very good news since the time required to physically pre-treat the biomass is reduced by a tenfold when targeting the larger particle size output.

The chemical treatment optimisation for the wheat straw returned similar results in terms of reduction of concentration of each of the species.

Further studies are still ongoing aiming at increasing the concentration of xylose and further remove the presence of inhibitors by filtration means ([9], [10], [11]).

Unfortunately, the results are not available at this time.

Regarding high-solid continuous pretreatment, preliminary assays were performed by CENER using wheat straw and miscanthus in order to reach high soluble sugars concentration at the end of the saccharification step as well as low inhibitors concentration. The thermochemical pretreatment conditions varied temperatures tested (from 160 up to 190°C) and acid catalyst added (from 0 up to 2.5% w/w). The slurries produced were characterized following NREL's procedures ([12], [13], [14]) and subjected to saccharification employing Dyadic CMAX5 enzymes. The results of the saccharification assays carried out with wheat straw and miscanthus are depicted in the following figures:

Figure 3: Total sugar concentration (g/L) at the end of the saccharification of wheat straw with a 10% of total solids. Inhibitors Acetic acid (AA) and furfural (FF) content (g/L) in the slurry's soluble fraction after thermochemical pretreatment.

Figure 4: Total sugar concentration (g/L) at the end of the saccharification of miscanthus with a 10% of total solids. Inhibitors Acetic acid (AA) and furfural (FF) content (g/L) in the slurry's soluble fraction after thermochemical pretreatment.

It has been demonstrated that all pretreatment conditions show an increase in glucose yield during saccharification both for wheat straw and miscanthus. Moreover, inhibitors concentration increased with severity in the thermochemical pretreatment. In case of wheat straw, high yields have been obtained regarding glucose and xylose solubilisation. By contrast results obtained with miscanthus show that there is still room for improving glucose saccharification.

In addition, the obtained results for wheat straw and miscanthus have been adjusted to a response curve to show the relationship between pretreatment conditions

(temperature and acid concentration) together with soluble sugar and inhibitors concentration.

3.2 Development and validation of high productivity butanol fermentation

The production of n-butanol with clostridial strains suffers from product inhibition, leading to low solvent titers and low productivities.

In work package 3, GBL aimed to improve fermentation performance by making and using next generation microorganisms that have an increased tolerance to feedstock derived inhibitors. GBL has developed and performed a continuous “feed and draw” method to naturally select robust fermentation microbes under a variety of growth conditions.

GBL have demonstrated at lab scale at least two sequential batch reactor (SBR) derived mixed cultures that are capable of better performance on inhibitory feedstocks and improved butanol tolerance than our current production strain. The best evolved cultures were assessed in GBL’s advanced fermentation process (AFP™). Evolved cultures showed >25% improved performance with respect to sugar uptake rate at higher residual butanol concentrations (30% higher than control cultures) and achieving a butanol yield exceeding the project target of 0.25 g/g on sugar consumed compared to the control.

AFP™ and nutrient optimisation were performed to improve the AFP™ process using lignocellulosic feedstock. The use of design of experiments (DoE) software and methods allowed rapid AFP optimisation.

An alleviation of product inhibition can be achieved by complementing the fermentation process with *in situ* product recovery (ISPR) technology. VITO’s ISPR approach consists of integrating organophilic pervaporation membranes to selectively remove the solvents. In earlier work 2-stage continuous fermentations were executed by VITO and optimized directly coupled with polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) based composite membranes. VITO could demonstrate major benefits of ISPR: an increased volumetric productivity (up to 1.13 g/L.h), solvent enrichment in the condensate (up to 200 g.kg⁻¹), decreased water consumption per kg solvents and a decreased energy consumption in the overall process (50% lower steam consumption). Fermentations were run for over 1 000 hours at stable membrane fluxes of 0.6 kg/m².h and without any sign of membrane fouling. Test work encompassed the use of pure glucose and mixed glucose-xylose feedstocks. In the framework of ButaNexT, earlier experimental work of VITO was expanded from continuous (Figure 5) to fed-batch operation, from two-stage to a single stage set-up, to micro-organisms with improved properties provided by GBL and to alternative pervaporation membranes. The shift to alternative membranes allowed to double fluxes while maintaining the high solvent enrichment in the condensate of the pervaporation. Continuous operation of a single-stage set-up allowed to reach productivities of 0.97 g/L.h, well above the 0.75 g/L.h target. These achievements further improve the economic case for ISPR.

Figure 5: Single stage continuous fermentation, directly coupled to pervaporation

3.3 Integration and pilot testing

WP4 is led by CENER and comprises the validation of the technical performance of the integrated process in a pilot facility covering the whole process from feedstock handling to product recovery

This approach will allow the integration of the individual conversion processes and biocatalysts (enzymes and microbes) developed in WPs 2 and 3

Although this WP does not start till month 13, during the previous months the following tasks have been carried out:

- Information collection from the equipment and process conditions of the individual process stages (WP2 and Wp3)
- Preliminary pilot plant lay-out definition

The first pilot plant assays are expected for the first quarter of 2017.

3.4 Blending, performance and emissions

In the case of diesel fuels, butanol cannot be used pure in diesel engines because it has lower density, viscosity, heating value, lubricity, flash point and cetane number. The main restrictive properties are flash point and cetane number, which would limit the butanol content to less than 5% in volume (see Figures 6 and 7). However, higher butanol contents could be used if some cetane number improvers are used and the standard is modified to require the use of flame arresters in tanks to avoid the auto-ignition during storage. Two blends were selected for further engine and vehicle tests: A first blend with 10% butanol with 90% diesel would represent a real scenario of implementation of butanol as renewable component for diesel fuels. A second blend with 20% butanol and 80% diesel would represent a future scenario, beyond 2020, in which higher renewable contents in diesel fuels are expected. If some biodiesel is included in the reference diesel fuel, many of the above mentioned properties are compensated by the biodiesel content. As observed in Figures 6 and 7, the presence of biodiesel in the blends would allow introducing higher contents of butanol. Consequently, a ternary blend with 10% butanol, 80% diesel and 10% biodiesel was proposed as optimal. This blend represents the commercial penetration of butanol in a hypothetical future scenario beyond 2020 if biodiesel remains in the market. In any case, any

initiative to promote the use of n-butanol in higher contents in diesel fuels would require the European Standardization for butanol as a blend component (similarly to ASTM D7862 [15]) and a modification of diesel standard (EN 590 [16]) to allow including certain butanol content.

Figure 6: Flash Point values for the different alcohol-diesel and alcohol-biodiesel blends

Figure 7: Derived cetane number values for the different alcohol-diesel and alcohol-biodiesel blends

With regard to gasoline blends, they can include up to 3.7% O₂ by mass to be commercialized. In this frame, the substitution of ethanol (up to 10% by volume) by n-butanol (up to 16% by volume) presents a series of benefits such as higher heating value or lower hygroscopic tendency compared to ethanol blends, what makes n-butanol a promising fuel for spark ignition engines. The higher heating value for butanol-gasoline blends would reduce the fuel consumption. When butanol is blended with gasoline, the vapour pressure decreases, and consequently, the blends would fulfil EN 228 [17]. However, the use of n-butanol in E85 blends substituting either gasoline or ethanol can cause cold start problems despite the lower enthalpy of vaporization of n-butanol. However, if the alcohol content in the baseline fuel is lower (70% for instance), replacing ethanol by n-butanol would be possible while remaining within the limits of the standard. A blend composed of 55 % ethanol, 15 % butanol and 30 % gasoline has been tested and it has been proved that the vapour pressure is above the lower limit, so it could be used in E85 vehicles.

All these tasks are being carried out by the University of Castilla la Mancha (UCLM).

3.5 Environmental, resource, techno-economic and social impact assessment

E4tech assessed the availability of several feedstocks within the EU that could be used to sustainably produce biobutanol, considering straw, miscanthus, municipal solid waste and woody residues.

Straw: Across all EU-28 countries the quantity of straw that could be extracted for biofuel production is estimated at 58M odt, assuming a 40% straw removal rate from the field, and accounting for alternative uses. There are particularly high reserves in France, Germany, Romania and Poland. However a commercial biobutanol plant will require a high geographic density of straw to avoid prohibitive costs and emissions from transportation. The areas with high straw production density are south-east England, central-northern France and Denmark. These areas may therefore represent the most appropriate location for a straw biobutanol plant in Europe, but consideration must be given to the wide range of alternative uses of straw and the impact that additional demand from a biobutanol plant may have on these sectors.

Miscanthus: To avoid ILUC (6), the cultivation of miscanthus should only be carried out on abandoned or degraded land. Several countries are shown to have significant abandoned land, and the potential for achieving high miscanthus yields: Italy, France, Northern Spain and Poland. Given that a commercial biobutanol plant would require in excess of 20,000ha of miscanthus feeding it, the greater prevalence of large farms in France and to a certain extent Spain would favour these countries for situation of a plant. Prior experience of growing miscanthus may also affect which countries are most attractive for situation of a miscanthus biobutanol plant.

MSW: The biological fraction of MSW does not have a high enough sugar content to be attractive for biobutanol production in the short term, but could be a viable feedstock in the future. Butanol production would require the separation of the biological fraction from the MSW, as currently practiced by Austria, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, Ireland, Italy, Poland and Navarra and Catalonia in Spain. However these countries are likely to already be utilizing the biological fraction, for example in AD or composting. Attractiveness of using MSW in butanol production compared to these competing uses will depend on plant economics and the waste hierarchy. France, UK, Italy, Spain and Poland have most waste currently going to landfill, so could have a significant untapped MSW resource for use in butanol production.

Woody Residues: Woody residues could be used in biobutanol production in the long-term, but are not a priority feedstock today. There is a large resource of prunings in Spain, Italy, France and Greece, which in some cases are just burned in the field. Sawmill residues and sawdust are produced in significant quantities in Sweden, Germany, Finland, France and Austria, but there are many competing uses for these materials and they are largely utilised at the moment. Countries with the largest potential for producing primary forestry residues are Sweden, Germany, Finland and France. Outside of Scandinavia these residues are often left in forests under current practices.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The main lessons learnt after ButaNexT's first year are the following:

- Among the three initially selected feedstocks, miscanthus and wheat straw are the ones that show higher sugar content and therefore, higher pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis yields. However the organic fiber from MSW has shown very poor performance in the pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis stages due to its low sugar content.
- After a complete characterization of the three feedstocks included in the study, an evaluation of the available milling technologies was carried out with the cutting mill selected as the best technology. After this, a few experiments were required to fine tune the milling mechanism before proceeding with a complete study on thermochemical pre-treatment optimisation. This study contemplated different scenarios in terms of temperatures, residence time and rheology of the slurry, which required a precise control on particle size. The results were consistent for both, the wheat straw and the miscanthus, and the pre-treatment operation was optimized both for improved yield and reduced energy consumption. Further studies are ongoing with the aim of drastically increasing the sugar concentration in the resulting liquid fraction by means of nanofiltration. Complementing this thermo-chemical pre-treatment, a physical pre-treatment prototype has been designed and is currently in the latest stages of construction. This prototype not only incorporates the functionalities related to controlling particle size but it also targets safety with regards of handling the fine powder produce by reducing particle emissions in a self-contained, air driven system.
- At least two SBR derived mixed cultures capable of better performance on inhibitory feedstocks and improved butanol tolerances have been carried out. The best evolved cultures have been assessed in advanced AFP™. These cultures have shown improved performance with respect to sugar uptake rate at higher residual butanol concentrations and butanol yields.
- Integration of organophilic pervaporation membranes with clostridial fermentation allowed alleviating product inhibition while achieving high solvent enrichment in the condensate of the pervaporation. Productivities of 0.97 g/L.h could be reached during continuous operation of a single-stage set-up with integrated pervaporation. This seems the optimal concept for upscaling.
- Butanol can be used a fuel blend component with both diesel and gasoline. It has better performance characteristics than existing biofuels (ethanol and biodiesel) and therefore, can be used in ternary blends to improve the properties of the final fuel (eg: e.g.: Butanol-Biodiesel-Diesel for diesel engines and Butanol-Ethanol-Gasoline for spark ignition engines).
- In the EU in the future, demand for biomass for energy and chemicals production is anticipated to increase, which may put increasing pressure on the availability of sustainably produced biomass, causing prices to increase. Nevertheless our

investigation showed that resources for butanol production are available in Europe, and identified the key countries and regions for each feedstock

5 NOTES

- (1) GHG: Greenhouse Gases
- (2) ABE: fermentation process named after the three products; acetone, butanol and ethanol.
- (3) E85: abbreviation for an ethanol fuel blend of 85% denatured ethanol fuel and 15% gasoline by volume.
- (4) DPF: Diesel particulate filter
- (5) ATEX: explosive atmospheres
- (6) ILUC: indirect land use change

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8 LOGO SPACE

More information about ButaNexT:

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